

THROMBOSIS OF THE CEREBRAL VEINS AND SINUSES

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Cerebral venous thrombosis (CVT) is rare, but more common than we think. The actual incidence of CVT remains unknown to date, and the available data (3-4 cases per 1 million population per year in adults and 7 cases per 1 million population in children) are based on the number of hospitalizations of patients with CVT in large hospitals. CVT is the cause of 1-2% of all strokes and occurs in all age groups, with peaks in neonates and adults in the 3rd decade of life; about 75% of patients are women. With CVT, ischemic cerebral infarcts often transform into hemorrhagic infarcts.

History reference. It is believed that the first description of cerebral venous sinus thrombosis (TCVS) and cerebral vein thrombosis belongs to the French physician Ribes, who in 1825 observed thrombosis of the sagittal sinus and cerebral veins in a man suffering from convulsions and delirium (Ribes M.F. Des recherches faites sur la phlebite // Rev. Med. Franc. Etrang. - 1825; 3: 5-41). Until the second half of the XX century. this diagnosis was usually made post-mortem. In the 40s of the twentieth century. Charles Symonds and others have reported the clinical diagnosis of CVT based on lumbar puncture findings and characteristic symptoms. Progress in diagnosis came in 1951 with the introduction of venography (Ray B.S., Dunbar H.S., Dotter C.T. Dural sinus venography as an aid to diagnosis in intracranial disease // J. Neurosurg. - 1951; 8 (1): 23-37), which also made it possible to differentiate the condition from idiopathic intracranial hypertension, which often manifests itself in this way in the form of CVT. Back in 1942, the British gynecologist Stansfield used heparin to treat CVT, but only in the 90s of the XX century. clinical studies have resolved the debate about the use of anticoagulants in most cases of CVT (source: angiology.com.ua)

Thrombosis of the lateral sinuses or superior sagittal sinus occurs most frequently. In 1/3 of cases, two or more sinuses are affected. In 30 - 40% of patients, the cerebral sinuses and cerebral or cerebellar veins are simultaneously involved in the pathological process. In the early stages of the disease, thrombosis of the cortical veins is possible without thrombosis of the venous sinuses - [!!!] the latter joins later, as a result of the progression of the thrombotic process.

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#1 VENOUS SYSTEM OF THE BRAIN

Etiology. About 100 etiological causes of CVT are known, which include all common causes of venous thrombosis, as well as a number of other causes associated with local anatomical features of the structure of the veins and sinuses of the dura mater. In 20 - 30% of cases, the etiology of CVT remains unknown (read more about the etiology and pathogenesis of CVT in the articles listed at the end of the post).

Pathogenesis. There are two pathogenetic options for the development of CVT - vein thrombosis with the formation of local damage to the brain tissue or thrombosis of the venous sinuses, leading to a sharp increase in intracranial pressure. Typically, thrombotic masses spread from the venous sinuses to smaller vessels. The main pathogenetic mechanism for the development of CVT is an increase in hydrostatic pressure in the proximal veins and capillaries, an increase in intracranial pressure, and the development of cytotoxic and vasogenic cerebral edema, the prevalence of which is usually directly proportional to the caliber of the thrombosed vein. In the zone of edema, stasis, diapedetic hemorrhages and multiple ischemic foci can develop. The

progression of the pathological process can lead to the development of ischemic or hemorrhagic cerebral infarction, the penetration of blood into the subarachnoid and subdural spaces. Up to 50% of cases of CVT are complicated by the development of edema of the brain substance and the formation of venous infarction and hemorrhagic complications.

Clinical picture. Diagnosis of CVT is rather difficult, since the manifestations of the disease are very variable: the clinical manifestations of CVT depend on the localization of thrombosis, the rate of its development, and the nature of the underlying disease. Severe disorders of venous circulation are characterized by headache, vomiting, edema of the optic discs, focal and generalized convulsions, and progressive depression of consciousness. However, with early recognition of the process, the clinical picture may be less pronounced. Focal neurological disorders may occur with isolated thrombosis of deep or superficial veins or with the spread of thrombosis from the sinuses to the veins. Meningeal syndrome is considered a rare manifestation of uncomplicated sinus thrombosis. The pressure of the cerebrospinal fluid, according to most authors, is normal or moderately elevated. The composition of the cerebrospinal fluid can be either unchanged or with a slightly increased protein content and pleocytosis no more than 200/3.

In most studies on the study of CVT, it was noted that the most frequent and early (first) symptom of CVT is headache (75 - 95% of cases), which is often the first reason for seeking medical help. It resembles the pain of a subarachnoid hemorrhage and is not relieved by analgesics. In addition, CVT reveals the following symptoms (in descending order of frequency): movement disorders, convulsive syndrome (including status epilepticus), psychomotor agitation, aphasia, visual disturbances, depression of consciousness (stupor, stupor, coma), disorders cranial nerve innervation, sensory disturbances, meningeal syndrome, vestibulo- cerebellar disorders.

Conclusion. When sinuses are affected, cerebral symptoms depend on the massiveness and rate of increase of thrombosis, and focal neurological symptoms correspond to the localization of the affected sinus. The most delineated syndrome, occurring in one third of patients, is isolated intracranial hypertension accompanied by hypertension and papilledema. As mentioned above, in the early stages of the disease, cortical vein thrombosis is possible without thrombosis of the venous sinuses. The latter joins later, as a result of the progression of the thrombotic process. There is no clear clinical syndrome indicating the development of this condition, however, the sudden onset of focal

symptoms and / or epileptic seizures is considered typical for this situation. Focal migratory symptoms appear when the substance of the brain is involved in the process with the development of first local cerebral edema, and then an extensive cortical venous infarction. Hemorrhagic infarction develops in 40% of patients with CVT. It is always necessary to consider the possibility of CVT in the presence of a hemorrhagic infarction with an acute onset of the disease.

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